

Journal of Energy Storage

Nickel-cobalt spinel-based oxygen evolution electrode for zinc-air flow battery

--Manuscript Draft--

Manuscript Number:	
Article Type:	Research Paper
Keywords:	Oxygen evolution electrode; Zinc-air flow battery; Nickel-cobalt spinel catalyst; Hybrid flow battery; mid-term stability; galvanostatic cycling
Corresponding Author:	Petr Mazúr University of Chemistry and Technology Prague Faculty of Chemical Engineering CZECH REPUBLIC
First Author:	Přemysl Ríchnr
Order of Authors:	Přemysl Ríchnr Jaromír Hnát Jiří Charvát Martin Bureš Jaromír Pociďč Martin Paidar Juraj Kosek Petr Mazúr
Abstract:	<p>Zinc-air flow battery (ZAFB) represents a candidate for safe, cheap and non-toxic stationary energy storage, however low efficiency of oxygen reactions on positive electrode still obstructs its commercialization. In our contribution, we aim to address this challenge by applying a NiCo₂O₄ electro-catalytic layer onto the selected 3D nickel-based electrodes for oxygen evolution reaction (OER) from highly alkaline electrolyte (battery charging reaction), by electrochemically-assisted deposition followed by calcination. The detailed physico-chemical characterization of the deposited layer (by SEM+EDX, XRD) confirmed homogeneous deposition of catalyst. The electrochemical characterization of the prepared electrodes was performed under defined conditions (temperature, state of charge) in three different set-ups using a complex methodology including voltammetry techniques, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, galvanostatic load and final charge-discharge cycling in the developed 3-electrodes 3-compartments battery full-cell. The results show that, for both substrates, the deposited NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer effectively lowers the battery overvoltage for OER. The better overall battery performance was achieved with the foam substrate, probably due to its higher surface area and more compact structure. The developed ZAFB with optimized OER electrode achieved stable and efficient performance at high current densities of 100 mA cm⁻², which is the highest reported one for cycling experiments, in a broad SoC range (0–80%) with energy efficiency of 42.1% and no decay of capacity utilization.</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	<p>Claudia Weidlich DECHEMA claudia.weidlich@dechema.de</p> <p>Thomas Turek Institute Director, TU Clausthal Institute of Chemical and Electrochemical Process Engineering turek@icvt.tu-clausthal.de</p> <p>Peter Fischer General Manager - Innovation Core, SEI automotive Europe GmbH peter.fischer@sei-ae.com</p>

Table 1: Detail of characterization procedure in the flow electrolysis cell.

Series	Procedures	Number of repetitions	
Series 1-5	Load curve (0 – 100 mA cm ⁻² , 1.25 mA cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	5×	5×
	Galvanostatic load (6 hours, 50 mA cm ⁻²)		
	125 min at OCV for bubbles removal	1×	
	Electrolyte exchange	1×	
Series 6	Load curve (0 – 100 mA cm ⁻² , 1.25 mA cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	2×	1×
	Galvanostatic load (6 hours, 50 mA cm ⁻²)		

Table 2: Evaluated parameters (first 4 parameters evaluated from load curves measurements), the description of parameters, time frame of parameters acquiring.

Parameter	Description of evaluation	Sampling time
ASR	Areas specific resistance, linear part of load curve, evaluated from current density range 15 – 50 mA cm ⁻²	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 5 th series 1 st repetition, 6 th series 2 nd repetition
$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-5}}$	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 5 th series 1 st repetition
$\Delta \eta_{\text{act}}$	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to actual OCP	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 5 th series 1 st repetition
$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-6}}$	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 6 th series 2 nd repetition
ΔOCP	Difference of measured OCPs	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 5 th series 1 st repetition
ΔpH	Difference of working electrolyte pH values	fresh working electrolyte and after 5 th series

Table 3: Overview of the electrochemical parameters of the oxygen evaluation reaction obtained from polarisation curves and Tafel analysis.

Mark	Electrode	Tafel slope (mV dec ⁻¹)	j_0 ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$)	η_{10} (V)	R2 (-)
1\$	Ni mesh	70	0.02		0.989
2\$	Ni mesh	186	89	0.3972	0.984
3\$	Ni mesh	447	3,320		0.987
1!	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni mesh	67	0.07	0.3462	0.997
1*	Ni foam	87	0.1		0.988
2*	Ni foam	193	59	0.4399	0.998
3*	Ni foam	353	1,298		0.995
1&	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni foam	84	1.1	0.3342	0.996
2&	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni foam	145	94		0.996

Table 4: Comparison of parameters change between at different stages of experiment evaluated from load curve measurements shown in **Figure 5**.

OER electrode	$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo. s.2-5}} /$ mV at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta \eta_{\text{act.}} /$ mV at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo. s.2-6}} /$ mV at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta \text{OCP} /$ mV	$\Delta \text{pH} / -$
Details of comparison	between series 2 and 5	between series 2 and 5	between series 2 and 6	between series 2 and 5	between series 1 and 5
Pristine mesh	82	24	14	58	-1.08
Catalysed mesh	75	23	21	44	-1.00
Pristine foam	69	36	3	62	-1.10
Catalysed foam	59	10	18	50	-1.06

Table 5: Zn-air battery single-cell parameters for the four tested nickel-based OER electrodes; 40 °C, 80 ml min⁻¹ electrolytes flow rate (0.7M ZnO dissolved in 8M KOH), 200 ml min⁻¹ air flow rate (technical, preheating to 40 °C). ASR evaluated from the EIS and load curve measurements at 50% SOC (in terms of neg. electrolyte), presented at Figure 9. Efficiencies and capacity utilization averaged from the values for 1-20 cycle, presented in **Figure 6**.

	$ASR_{\Omega-c}$	$ASR_{\Omega-d}$	$ASR_{\text{tot-c}}$	$ASR_{\text{tot-d}}$	CE	VE	EE	CU
OER electrode	Ohm cm ²	Ohm cm ²	Ohm cm ²	Ohm cm ²	%	%	%	%
Pristine mesh	1.26	1.64	3.00	3.34	95.4	34.8	33.2	77
Catalyzed mesh	1.28	1.64	2.50	3.02	95.4	37.5	35.8	77
Pristine foam	1.30	1.50	2.42	3.56	92.3	34.8	32.1	74
Catalyzed foam	1.20	1.56	2.16	2.84	94.9	44.4	42.1	78

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Figure 1: **a)** Flow electrolysis cell for preliminary testing of OER electrode; **b)** Schematics of testing apparatus for characterization of developed OER electrode in the electrolysis cell; **c)** Developed 3-electrode 3-compartment ZAFB single-cell; **d)** Schematics of testing apparatus for characterization of developed OER electrode in ZAFB: 1) ZAFB cell; 2) electrolyte tank; 3) air gas cylinder; 4) air pre-heating.

Figure 2: Images from scanning electron microscope for: (A) pristine nickel mesh, (B) NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, (C) detail of NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer, (D) detail of NiCo₂O₄ particles, (E) fresh NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, (F) used NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode.

Figure 3: Distribution of selected elements on surface of Ni mesh/NiCo₂O₄ electrode determined by SEM-EDS mapping of surface. (A) SEM image of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode; (B) distribution of Ni; (C) distribution of Co; (D) distribution of O.

Figure 4: Images from scanning electron microscope for: (A) pristine nickel foam, (B) NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode, (C) detail of NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer, (D) detail of NiCo₂O₄ particles, (E) fresh NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode, (F) used NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode.

Figure 5: Distribution of selected elements on surface nickel foam electrode determined by SEM-EDS mapping of surface. (A) SEM image of $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ foam electrode; (B) distribution of Ni; (C) distribution of Co; (D) distribution of O.

Figure 6: a) Load curves and b) Tafel curves for pristine and catalytically activated Ni substrates at current density 0 – 100 mA cm⁻² and geometric area of electrodes was 1 cm². The potential is IR compensated. Pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). **Working conditions:** 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH, 25 °C, RHE reference electrode, current scan rate of 1 mA s⁻¹ cm⁻².

Figure 7: **a)** Evolution of OER electrode potential within the mid-term stability experiment for the four Ni-based electrodes: pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). **b)** Initial load curves of the four tested OER electrodes taken from the 1st repetition of series 2; **c)** Load curves for PM and CM electrodes. **d)** Comparison of ASR (left bar) and η_{theo} (right bar, lighter color) evaluated from dynamic load curves. I - after initial stabilization (2nd series, 1st repetition), A - last series before electrolyte exchange (5th series 1st repetition), E - after electrolyte exchange (6th series 2nd repetition). **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH, electrolyte flow rate 160 ml min⁻¹, 20 °C, constant load for 6 hours at 50 mA cm⁻², load curve measurements (0–100 mA cm⁻², 1.25 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹), 5 series (each consists of 5 repetitions) and 2 more repetition after electrolyte change.

Figure 8: **a)** EIS spectra (C – charge connection, D – discharge connection), **b)** charging and discharging dynamic load curves and **c)** discharging load curves and power curves of Zn-air battery single-cell for the four tested Ni-based OER electrodes at 50% SOC (with respect to the electrolyte composition); LC-load curve, PC-power curve; **d)** Development of efficiencies (EE – energy efficiency, CE – coulombic efficiency) and capacity utilization (CU – capacity utilization) of during galvanostatic-potentiostatic cycling at 100 mA cm^{-2} ; General conditions: $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 80 ml min^{-1} electrolytes flow rate (0.7 mol dm^{-3} ZnO dissolved in 8 mol dm^{-3} KOH), 200 ml min^{-1} air flow (technical, preheated to $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). PM – pristine mesh, CM – catalyzed mesh, PF – pristine foam, CF – catalyzed foam.

Click here to access/download
Supplementary Material
Supplementary.docx

Figure 1: **a)** Flow electrolysis cell for preliminary testing of OER electrode; **b)** Schematics of testing apparatus for characterization of developed OER electrode in the electrolysis cell; **c)** Developed 3-electrode 3-compartment ZAFB single-cell; **d)** Schematics of testing apparatus for characterization of developed OER electrode in ZAFB: 1) ZAFB cell; 2) electrolyte tank; 3) air gas cylinder; 4) air pre-heating.

Figure 2: Images from scanning electron microscope for: (A) pristine nickel mesh, (B) NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, (C) detail of NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer, (D) detail of NiCo₂O₄ particles, (E) fresh NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, (F) used NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode.

Figure 3: Distribution of selected elements on surface of Ni mesh/NiCo₂O₄ electrode determined by SEM-EDS mapping of surface. (A) SEM image of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode; (B) distribution of Ni; (C) distribution of Co; (D) distribution of O.

Figure 4: Images from scanning electron microscope for: (A) pristine nickel foam, (B) NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode, (C) detail of NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer, (D) detail of NiCo₂O₄ particles, (E) fresh NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode, (F) used NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode.

Figure 5: Distribution of selected elements on surface nickel foam electrode determined by SEM-EDS mapping of surface. (A) SEM image of NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode; (B) distribution of Ni; (C) distribution of Co; (D) distribution of O.

Figure 6: **a)** Load curves and **b)** Tafel curves for pristine and catalytically activated Ni substrates at current density 0 – 100 mA cm⁻² and geometric area of electrodes was 1 cm². The potential is IR compensated. Pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). **Working conditions:** 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH, 25 °C, RHE reference electrode, current scan rate of 1 mA s⁻¹ cm⁻².

Figure 7: **a)** Evolution of OER electrode potential within the mid-term stability experiment for the four Ni-based electrodes: pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). **b)** Initial load curves of the four tested OER electrodes taken from the 1st repetition of series 2; **c)** Load curves for PM and CM electrodes. **d)** Comparison of ASR (left bar) and η_{theo} (right bar, lighter color) evaluated from dynamic load curves. I - after initial stabilization (2nd series, 1st repetition), A - last series before electrolyte exchange (5th series 1st repetition), E - after electrolyte exchange (6th series 2nd repetition). **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH, electrolyte flow rate 160 ml min⁻¹, 20 °C, constant load for 6 hours at 50 mA cm⁻², load curve measurements (0–100 mA cm⁻², 1.25 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹), 5 series (each consists of 5 repetitions) and 2 more repetition after electrolyte change.

Figure 8: **a)** EIS spectra (C – charge connection, D – discharge connection), **b)** charging and discharging dynamic load curves and **c)** discharging load curves and power curves of Zn-air battery single-cell for the four tested Ni-based OER electrodes at 50% SOC (with respect to the electrolyte composition); LC-load curve, PC-power curve; **d)** Development of efficiencies (EE – energy efficiency, CE – coulombic efficiency) and capacity utilization (CU – capacity utilization) of during galvanostatic-potentiostatic cycling at 100 mA cm⁻²; General conditions: 40 °C, 80 ml min⁻¹ electrolytes flow rate (0.7 mol dm⁻³ ZnO dissolved in 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH), 200 ml min⁻¹ air flow (technical, preheated to 40 °C). PM – pristine mesh, CM – catalysed mesh, PF – pristine foam, CF – catalysed foam.

Highlights

- Oxygen evolution reaction (OER) electrodes for zinc-air flow battery (ZAFB) developed.
- Enhanced performance of ZAFB full-cell with nickel-cobalt spinel OER catalyst.
- Efficient and stable performance over 180 hours of current load at 50 mA cm^{-2} .
- Increased cycle efficiency by 10% compared to pristine Ni substrate (mesh, foam).

22nd October 2024

Dear Editor,

I would like to thank you for your time when considering our work: “Nickel-cobalt spinel-based oxygen evolution electrode for zinc-air flow battery” which we are submitting for exclusive consideration of publication as a research article in the Journal of Energy Storage. The paper is approved by all authors and host authorities. In this work, we propose the systematic study of oxygen evolution reaction (OER) positive electrode development using NiCo₂O₄ spinel electrocatalyst for the charging reaction of zinc-air flow battery ZAFB in 3-electrodes 3-compartments single-cell set-up. The prepared electrodes were tested in three different arrangements incl.: a non-flow electrolysis cell, an electrolysis cell under flowing electrolyte conditions and finally in the ZAFB single-cell. The study involves comparison of two different electrode substrates: nickel mesh and nickel foam by a complex characterization protocol incl. electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, steady-state load curves and galvanostatic charge-discharge cycles, to assess distribution of resistances within the cell as well as the efficiencies and performance stability.

For both electrode substrates, the application of the catalyst layer significantly improved the battery performance (increased energy and voltaic efficiency up to 10%) due to reduced activation polarization of OER. Even more, a stable performance was observed even after 180 hours of mid-term characterization in a flow electrolysis cell. The nickel foam-based electrodes provided us with slightly better performance stability of the ZAFB full-cell cycling, due to the reduced flooding of the ORR electrode by the electrolyte.

To best of our knowledge, our work presents the first systematic study of OER positive electrode development using NiCo₂O₄ spinel electrocatalyst for the charging reaction of ZAFB in 3-electrodes 3-compartments single-cell set-up. The main contribution and novelty of our study can be summarized as follows:

- The application of catalyst layer on two different OER substrates was systematically studied in three different experimental set-ups: from initial 3-electrode voltametric analysis, through stability tests in a flow electrolyser up to final testing in the developed lab-scale ZAFB full-cell.
- Detail physico-chemical analysis of the electrodes (XRD, SEM+EDS), prior and after mid-term testing, is done to see the initial distribution of the catalyst layer over the substrate and the changes caused by the testing.
- For both Ni substrates, the deposition of NiCo₂O₄ spinel electrocatalyst decreased the charging overvoltage by 200 mV (at 50 mA cm⁻²) compared to pristine substrate and the electrode performance remained stable even within 180 hours of mid-term current loading in the flow electrolysis cell (at 50 mA cm⁻²).
- The nickel foam-based OER electrode provided slightly better initial performance and extended life-time of lab-scale ZAFB full-cell: average energy efficiency of 42.1% for galvanostatic cycling at 100 mA cm⁻² within a broad SOC range (0–80% SoC) at 40 °C and no decay of capacity utilization.

- The achieved intensification of the ZAFB operation at low catalyst loading and high capacity utilization of the electrolyte is an important step towards the industrial application of the system for stationary energy storage within the ongoing energy transformation.

Please, do not hesitate to contact me in any case of need.

Best regards,

Dr. Petr Mazúr
Department of Chemical Engineering
University of Chemistry and Technology Prague
Czechia (European Union)
e-mail: mazurp@vscht.cz
phone: +420 22044 3360

Nickel-cobalt spinel-based oxygen evolution electrode for zinc-air flow battery

Přemysl Richtr^a, Jaromír Hnát^b, Jiří Charvát^c, Martin Bureš^a, Jaromír Pocedič^c, Martin Paidar^b, Juraj Kosek^{a, c}, Petr Mazúr^{a, c}

^aUniversity of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Department of Chemical Engineering, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

^bUniversity of Chemistry and Technology Prague, Department of Inorganic Technology, Technická 5, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

^cNew Technologies – Research Centre, University of West Bohemia, Univerzitní 8, 306 14, Plzeň, Czech Republic

Abstract

Zinc-air flow battery (ZAFB) represents a candidate for safe, cheap and non-toxic stationary energy storage, however low efficiency of oxygen reactions on positive electrode still obstructs its commercialization. In our contribution, we aim to address this challenge by applying a NiCo₂O₄ electro-catalytic layer onto the selected 3D nickel-based electrodes for oxygen evolution reaction (OER) from highly alkaline electrolyte (battery charging reaction), by electrochemically-assisted deposition followed by calcination. The detailed physico-chemical characterization of the deposited layer (by SEM+EDX, XRD) confirmed homogeneous deposition of catalyst. The electrochemical characterization of the prepared electrodes was performed under defined conditions (temperature, state of charge) in three different set-ups using a complex methodology including voltammetry techniques, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, galvanostatic load and final charge-discharge cycling in the developed 3-electrodes 3-compartments battery full-cell. The results show that, for both substrates, the deposited NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer effectively lowers the battery overvoltage for OER. The better overall battery performance was achieved with the foam substrate, probably due to its higher surface area and more compact structure. The developed ZAFB with optimized OER electrode achieved stable and efficient performance at high current densities of 100 mA cm⁻², which is the highest reported one for cycling experiments, in a broad SoC range (0–80%) with energy efficiency of 42.1% and no decay of capacity utilization.

1. Introduction

Transition of the energy sector towards higher share of renewable sources represents part of global plans for carbon neutral energetics. However, renewable energy sources are mostly characterized by time-varying performance. Thus, for their optimal use, it is necessary to combine them with stationary energy storage of sufficient power and capacity. Stationary storage increases the accessibility of energy from renewable sources by stabilizing and shifting the power curve. In recent years, the installed capacity of electrochemical storage has been increasing rapidly worldwide [1]. Due to their high longevity, robustness and operational safety, vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFBs) represent nowadays one of the promising solutions for large-scale energy

1
2
3
4 storage. However, due to limited mineral resources, significant deployment of VRFBs is limited
5 by the high acquisition cost [2]. Therefore, there is an intensive search for more investment-
6 affordable energy storage alternatives. Zinc is attractive metal for energy storage both in static or
7 under flowing conditions, where flowing arrangement can extend durability of zinc battery [3].
8 Zinc-air flow battery (ZAFB), due to its non-toxicity, high availability of electrolyte precursors
9 and thus lower input costs, appears to be a suitable candidate for stationary electrical energy
10 storage [4]. Intensive research and development of the technology is currently taking place,
11 including following activities: optimization of internal cell components [5], assembly of laboratory
12 cells [6-8], and testing of semi-operational units with power and capacity in the order of kW and
13 kWh units respectively [9]. However, ZAFB has not been commercialized yet, mainly due to its
14 limited durability. The main limiting factors include uneven deposition and dissolution of zinc,
15 which affects both the stability and capacity of the system. Other disadvantages are the sluggish
16 kinetics of the positive electrode oxygen reactions limiting the energy efficiency of the system and
17 the limited chemical stability of the battery components in strongly alkaline electrolytes [10].

22
23 ZAFB utilize oxygen evolution reaction (OER) for charging and oxygen reduction reaction (ORR)
24 for discharging at positive electrode, according to **eq. 1** (written in charging direction).

27
28
29
30
31 This comes along with reduced battery size and costs per capacity, as in principle, only caustic
32 solution is needed for battery charge and atmospheric oxygen for its discharge. In reality, these
33 advantages are accompanied with several challenges related to the need for catalyst utilization and
34 more sophisticated construction of positive electrode (when compared, e.g. to std. RFB with only
35 liquid and solid phases). ZAFBs cells can either use a single oxygen electrode with bi-functional
36 catalyst for both OER and ORR or two separate electrodes dedicated to each reaction [11, 12]. Bi-
37 functional positive electrode is favourable from constructional point of view as it simplifies the
38 construction of battery stack enabling a relatively simple bipolar arrangement. However,
39 performance and stability of bi-functional catalyst is typically significantly lower when compared
40 to the 3-electrode set-up, as it is hard to fulfil the requirements of the two different processes
41 (transport of electrons and fluids, corrosion stability, catalytic activity) [3]. This also includes the
42 choice of suitable supporting material for the electrode. The conventional ORR electrodes use
43 carbon-based gas diffusion layer, typically containing hydrophobic polymeric binder, for securing
44 that the air gets to the catalytic layer of electrode while the electrolyte does not penetrate through
45 the electrode. These electrodes were adopted from hydrogen-oxygen fuel cell technology, where
46 they are commonly used [11]. Unfortunately, carbon-based components are unstable at high
47 potentials needed for oxygen evolution, which prevents the use of carbon-based gas diffusion
48 electrode for OER [13]. Instead, nickel-based electrodes are typically used for OER [14], which
49 are known from alkaline water electrolysis [3]. Need for separation of OER and ORR electrodes,
50 typically realized by porous diaphragm or separator, increases the complexity of the battery design,
51 the overall ohmic resistance of the cell and requires the combined multi-cell battery stack set-up
52 with monopolar (charging) and bipolar (discharging) electrode [11].
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 Nickel foam is the most widely used as ZAFB electrode material due to its sufficient stability
5 under OER conditions (at highly alkaline pH, which is needed for high solubility of zincate ions)
6 and relatively high surface area available for the reaction. Complex OER mechanism including 4-
7 electron transfer is characterized by high activation energy barrier [15] which significantly limits
8 the overall energy efficiency of ZAFB operation (same is true for hydrogen alkaline electrolyzers
9 [16]). Therefore, researcher's interest is to find high performance and stable electrocatalyst for the
10 OER. The activation barrier of OER can be decreased by several electrocatalysts, among those
11 noble metal oxides, IrO₂ and RuO₂, are state of the art catalysts with the highest OER activity [17].
12 Despite their superior activity and sufficient stability, these catalysts are expensive. Since the
13 ZAFBs are typically operated with alkaline electrolytes, some much cheaper, but still relatively
14 stable alternatives can be used, such as Fe, Co and Ni based compounds [18]. The recent review
15 on catalyst for OER in alkaline and neutral media provides overview of all possible catalysts [16].
16 The NiCo₂O₄ spinel catalyst has been reported in several publications as a suitable electrocatalyst
17 for OER in zinc-air batteries[19-24]. While all these studies deals with the static type of
18 rechargeable zinc-air battery, so far only a single study has mentioned the behaviour of this
19 promising catalyst as part of bifunctional catalyst under electrolyte-flow conditions, i.e. in ZAFB
20 [25]. To best of our knowledge, our work presents the first systematic study of OER positive
21 electrode development using NiCo₂O₄ spinel electrocatalyst for the charging reaction of ZAFB in
22 3-electrodes 3-compartments single-cell set-up. The study includes: i) optimization of electrode
23 preparation by electrochemically assisted deposition of the electrocatalyst on two different Ni-
24 based substrates (mesh, foam) and subsequent calcination of the layer; ii) detailed physico-
25 chemical characterization of the deposited catalysts prior and after the mid-term cell testing; and
26 iii) complex electrochemical characterization of the prepared electrodes under well-defined
27 conditions (temperature, current load) in non-flow and flow-through laboratory electrochemical
28 cells. The mid-term stability of the electrodes was confirmed by flow electrolyser testing for up to
29 180 hours. Experiments in the developed laboratory ZAFB are carried out in a broad range of SoC
30 (0 – 80% of the negative electrolyte), which is not common for ZAFB in literature.
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40

41 2. Experimental

42 2.1 Preparation of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode

43 For the preparation of catalytically activated electrodes, nickel foam (99 %, Inco Advanced
44 Technology Materials Co., Ltd, thickness 1.7 mm, pore size 580 μm) and nickel mesh (95 %,
45 Bibus Metals s.r.o, 0.9 mm thickness) substrates were selected and electrochemically-assisted
46 deposition of the catalytic layer was used. The deposition solution consists of 1.813 g of
47 Ni(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and 3.630 g Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O in 1 dm³ of demineralized water (DEMI, specific
48 conductivity < 0.5 μS cm⁻¹). Prior to the deposition, substrates were pre-treated by sonication in
49 ethanol for 2× 0.5 hour with change of ethanol between the cleanings. Deposition of the catalytic
50 layer was performed in two-electrode arrangement with pre-treated substrate (geometrical surface
51 9×7 cm²), connected as cathode, and IrO₂ activated Ti rod as anode. Deposition was done in a
52 galvanostatic mode at a geometrical current density of 0.8 mA cm⁻² at 25 °C for 1.5 hour. Substrate
53 with the deposited Ni(OH)₂/Co(OH)₂ layer was subsequently rinsed in the demineralized water for
54 several times to remove the residues of the deposition solution. The prepared samples were dried
55 at ambient air for 12 hours. After drying, the samples were calcinated in the air atmosphere at
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4 325 °C for 4 hours. Temperature rise during the calcination was 4 °C min⁻¹. During calcination
5 step, NiCo₂O₄ layer was formed on the Ni substrate. Catalyst loading was equivalent of 1 mg
6 NiCo₂O₄ per cm². The following nickel-based OER electrodes were prepared and characterized:
7 pristine nickel foam, pristine nickel mesh, catalytically activated nickel foam and catalytically
8 activated nickel mesh.
9

10 11 2.2 Electrochemical characterization in liquid electrolyte non-flow arrangement

12 Electrochemical characterization of the prepared OER electrodes in a non-flow electrolyte set-up
13 was done in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH solution at 25 °C using three-electrode arrangement. The prepared
14 electrode with geometrical area of 1 cm² was used as working electrode, reversible hydrogen
15 electrode (RHE) was used as reference electrode (all potentials are thus related to RHE) and a
16 nickel wire was used as counter electrode (CE). Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS)
17 was used to evaluate the ohmic resistance of the system. EIS was performed at frequencies
18 100 kHz – 0.1 Hz with voltage amplitude of the perturbing signal 10 mV at 0 vs. RHE. Linear
19 sweep voltammetry was used to measure OER polarization curves within a current density range
20 0 – 100 mA cm⁻² (with current sweep rate of 1 mA s⁻¹ cm⁻²). Tafel analysis was used to evaluate
21 exchange current density, which represents the kinetic parameter of the OER and Tafel slope,
22 which is connected with the rate-determination step.
23
24
25
26
27

28 2.3 Construction of the flow cells

29 To suppress the instability of ZAFB due to the other electrodes (zinc and ORR electrode) the
30 prepared OER electrodes were firstly tested in a laboratory flow electrolysis single-cell with
31 hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) taking place at a pristine nickel mesh CE. The schematics of
32 the flow electrolysis cell is shown in **Figure 1a** (construction derived from std. lab-cell by Pinflow
33 energy storage, s.r.o.). It consists of aluminium end plates, nickel current collectors, elastomeric
34 polyolefin-based flat gaskets, electrolyte distribution frames made of polytetrafluorethylene
35 (PTFE), ion-exchange membrane Nafion N115 (Chemours) and polypropylene PP-based static
36 mixers (SM). The membrane was pre-activated in different baths at 80 °C: one hour in
37 demineralized water, 30 minutes in H₂O₂, and 30 minutes in 1 mol dm⁻³ KOH bath. The geometric
38 area of the electrodes was 20 cm². Flow-through distribution of electrolyte was used for both half-
39 cell compartments, which were filled with PP-based SM to enhance the homogeneity of the
40 electrolyte flow.
41
42
43
44
45

46 **Figure 1c** shows a schematic of the developed ZAFB single-cell (construction derived from std.
47 lab-cell by Pinflow energy storage, s.r.o.) in 3-electrodes 3-compartments set-up (i.e. using two
48 separated positive electrodes and compartments for charging (OER) and discharging (ORR)
49 reactions). Carbon-polymer composite plate PPG 86 (Eisenhuth) and graphite felt (provided by
50 Pinflow energy storage, s.r.o., 20 cm² electrode area, compression ratio 25 %, thermally activated
51 according to [26]) served as negative electrode. OER took place in the middle of the flow
52 compartment, which was hydraulically separated from negative electrode compartment by anion-
53 exchange membrane FAAM 20 (Fumatech) and from positive ORR compartment by porous PP-
54 based separator (Celgard 5500 by Celgard). The membrane was first heat treated in air atmosphere
55 for 20 min at 260 °C and then activated by soaking in 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH solution at 40 °C for 24
56 hours, according to recommendation of the producer. ORR electrode consisted of a carbon paper-
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

based gas diffusion layer (GDL BC 28, provided SGL) with the ink-spray deposited catalytic layer with commercial platinum-based electrocatalyst on carbon support (HiSPEC 4000 by Alfa Aesar, Pt loading of 0.5 mg cm^{-2}) and PTFE binder (60 wt.% in cat. layer, PTFE suspension Alglofon by Solvay). Carbon-polymer composite plate PPG 86 (Eisenhuth) with milled 1 mm wide and deep channels serpentine flow field served for distribution of air to ORR electrode. A lab-made electronic device was used to switch the connection to potentiostat between charging and discharging mode (see **Figure S1**).

Figure 1: **a)** Flow electrolysis cell for preliminary testing of OER electrode; **b)** Schematics of testing apparatus for characterization of developed OER electrode in the electrolysis cell; **c)** Developed 3-electrode 3-compartment ZAFB single-cell; **d)** Schematics of testing apparatus for characterization of developed OER electrode in ZAFB: 1) ZAFB cell; 2) electrolyte tank; 3) air gas cylinder; 4) air pre-heating.

2.4 Electrochemical characterization in liquid electrolyte flow arrangement

Testing apparatus (see **Figure 1b**) for the preliminary testing of the prepared OER electrodes under the electrolyte flow conditions consisted of a flow electrolysis cell, peristaltic pump (Watson Marlow), two separated electrolyte tanks and tubing connecting tanks with the cell. Each tank contained 0.5 dm³ aqueous solution of 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH electrolyte. Evolving oxygen bubbles significantly increases overall resistance of battery and therefore it is desirable to remove bubbles effectively [11]. To enhance bubble removal and minimize effect of the electrolyte bubbling, the flow rate of electrolyte was set to 160 ml min⁻¹, i.e. double value with respect to the final testing in ZAFB single-cell. Mercury-mercury oxide reference electrode (MOE; Hg/HgO with potential of 0.098 V vs. NHE) was positioned on the outlet of the positive half-cell via a Luggin capillary. The whole testing apparatus was placed in a temperature-insulated box tempered at given temperature of 20 °C.

The prepared electrodes were characterized in a flow electrolysis cell by a procedure consisting of dynamic load curves, and galvanostatic loads. A battery cycler BCS-815 (BioLogic) was used to accomplish this task. Load curve (LC) measurements were performed in the range 0 – 100 mA cm⁻² with linear current density increase of 1.25 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹. Galvanostatic load was set on 50 mA cm⁻² for 6 hours. Each repetition consists of following steps LC and galvanostatic load. There were five repetitions followed by 125 minutes long pause for removing all the bubbles from the flow cell and from the electrolyte tanks, this is called series. There were five series (25 repetitions in sum) followed by change of electrolyte and two more repetitions (6th series) were done (summed up in **Table 1**). Total time of whole characterization was over 180 hours.

Table 1: Detail of characterization procedure in the flow electrolysis cell.

Series	Procedures	Number of repetitions	
Series 1-5	Load curve (0 – 100 mA cm ⁻² , 1.25 mA cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	5×	5×
	Galvanostatic load (6 hours, 50 mA cm ⁻²)		
	125 min at OCV for bubbles removal	1×	
	Electrolyte exchange	1×	
Series 6	Load curve (0 – 100 mA cm ⁻² , 1.25 mA cm ⁻² s ⁻¹)	2×	1×
	Galvanostatic load (6 hours, 50 mA cm ⁻²)		

From the load curves the following parameters were evaluated (for further description see **Table 2**): area specific resistance *ASR* (linear part of load curve for current density range 15 – 50 mA cm⁻²

²), OER overpotential at 50 mA cm⁻² to theoretical OCP (η_{theo} , theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE) of positive electrode under given conditions. The actual OCP was changing through 5 series, probably due to the electrolyte pH change, therefore change of OCP (Δ OCP) and actual overpotential was evaluated (η_{act}). The pH change (Δ pH) was evaluated.

Table 2: Evaluated parameters (first 4 parameters evaluated from load curves measurements), the description of parameters, time frame of parameters acquiring.

Parameter	Description of evaluation	Sampling time
ASR	Areas specific resistance, linear part of load curve, evaluated from current density range 15 – 50 mA cm ⁻²	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 5 th series 1 st repetition, 6 th series 2 nd repetition
$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-5}}$	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 5 th series 1 st repetition
$\Delta \eta_{\text{act}}$	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to actual OCP	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 5 th series 1 st repetition
$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-6}}$	Difference of OER overpotential (50 mA cm ⁻²) with respect to theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 6 th series 2 nd repetition
Δ OCP	Difference of measured OCPs	2 nd series 1 st repetition, 5 th series 1 st repetition
Δ pH	Difference of working electrolyte pH values	fresh working electrolyte and after 5 th series

2.5 Characterization procedure in alkaline zinc-air flow battery

Testing apparatus (see **Figure 1d**) for testing of the prepared OER electrodes in ZAFB consisted of a ZAFB single-cell cell (detail description in **section 2.3**), peristaltic pump (Watson Marlow), mass flow meter (Omega), reference electrode MOE (Equilibrium) and a single electrolyte tank and tubing connecting tank with the cell. Technical air was preheated (by passing a 1 m long steel capillary submerged in the water bath tempered at 40 °C. The air was used for ORR with a flow rate of 200 ml min⁻¹ controlled by flow mass meter. Both negative and positive charging electrodes were supplied with a single electrolyte using the peristaltic pump, std. electrolyte flowrate of 80 ml min⁻¹. Electrolyte consisted of 0.7 mol dm⁻³ ZnO dissolved in 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH. The whole testing apparatus was placed in a temperature-insulated box tempered at given temperature of 40 °C.

1
2
3
4 All the OER electrodes were tested in a zinc-air flow battery cell by a developed characterization
5 protocol consisting of: EIS, dynamic load curves and combined galvanostatic-potentiostatic
6 charge-discharge cycling. A potentiostat VSP-300 with 4A booster (BioLogic) was used for the
7 testing. Firstly, the battery was galvanostatically charged to theoretical 50% SoC (with respect to
8 zincate concentration in the electrolyte) using current density of 100 mA cm^{-2} . At this SoC EIS
9 and load curves characterizations were performed. EIS was measured in OCV at potentiostatic
10 mode in the frequency range from 100 kHz to 1 Hz with a sinus amplitude of 10 mV for both,
11 charge and discharge mode of the battery. The load curve measurements for battery charging and
12 discharging were performed in $0 - 200 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ range with linear increase $5 \text{ mA cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$.
13 Subsequently, a galvanostatic charge-discharge cycling of the battery was performed at
14 100 mA cm^{-2} in $0 - 80\%$ SoC range; charging was always terminated by the charge (80% of
15 theoretical capacity of zincate ions in the electrolyte), discharging cut-off voltage was 0.5 V (for
16 galvanostatic discharging) followed by potentiostatic discharge at 0.5 V until the current density
17 drops below 10% of charging current density (10 mA cm^{-2}).
18
19
20
21
22

23 From EIS the charge $ASR_{\Omega-c}$ and discharge $ASR_{\Omega-d}$ area specific ohmic resistances of the measured
24 system were evaluated as high-frequency intercept of Nyquist diagram with x-axis. The charge
25 and discharge area specific resistances (ASR_{tot-c} , ASR_{tot-d}) of battery cell were evaluated from the
26 slope of linear part of corresponding load curves (current density region of $50 - 200 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$).
27
28

29 2.6 Scanning electron microscopy and energy-dispersive spectroscopy

30 For the characterization of the OER electrode samples prior and after their battery testing, the
31 scanning electron microscope (SEM) Hitachi S4700 was used in the secondary electron mode.
32 Accelerating voltage 15 kV and emission current $10 \mu\text{A}$ was used. Microscope Hitachi S4700 was
33 equipped with SD (silicon drifted) detector of X-ray which enabled energy dispersive spectroscopy
34 (EDS). Lateral resolution of detector is $1 \mu\text{m}^2$ with sensitivity of 10–100 ppm. Precision of
35 measurement is up to 1 wt.%. Accelerating voltage 15 kV and emissive current $20 \mu\text{A}$ was used.
36 EDS analysis was done in mapping of surface mode with $30\times$ magnification and in mode surface
37 analysis with $500\times$ magnification.
38
39
40
41

42 2.7 X-ray diffraction analysis

43 X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis of the prepared OER samples was done with Co cathode that
44 allows more precise determination of phases with presence of Ni. Spectra were measured from
45 2° to 110° (2Θ) with step 0.039° (2Θ). Accelerating voltage of electron generator was 35 kV.
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

3. Results

The primary aim of this study was to decrease overpotential of the OER electrode in alkaline ZAFB. The result section is divided into the two parts. First one is focused on physico-chemical characterization of the self-prepared catalytically activated OER electrodes by electrochemically assisted deposition of a thin NiCo_2O_4 catalytic layer onto the surface of nickel-based substrates (nickel foam and nickel mesh). The second part shows the results of electrochemical characterization of the electrodes in three different set-ups: i) batch experiments in static electrolyte, ii) performance and stability testing in flow electrolysis cell and iii) final electrode testing in 3-electrode 3-compartment ZAFB single-cell.

3.1 Physico-chemical characterization of the prepared OER electrode

3.1.1 XRD characterization of OER electrodes

Phase composition of the prepared catalytic layer was confirmed by XRD (see **Figure S2**), which revealed presence of the Ni phase, which is present due to the Ni mesh and NiCo_2O_4 phase. Synthesis of the NiCo_2O_4 catalyst was thus confirmed.

3.1.2 SEM+EDS

Figure 2 shows comparison of SEM images of pristine nickel mesh (**Figure 2A**) and the nickel mesh modified by NiCo_2O_4 catalytic layer (**Figure 2B, C, D**). The images illustrate that the catalytic layer is homogeneously deposited over the Ni surface. **Figure 2C** shows the presence of the cracks in the deposited layer, which were most probably formed during the calcination due to the transformation of the $\text{Ni}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ precursors to NiCo_2O_4 . As it is visible from detail image of the catalytic layer (**Figure 2D**), size of the catalyst particles is in order of units of micrometres. **Figure 2E, F** shows comparison of the freshly prepared electrode and electrode after stability testing. Comparison of the catalytic layers does not show significant changes in the morphology of the catalytic layer after testing.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 2: Images from scanning electron microscope for: (A) pristine nickel mesh, (B) NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, (C) detail of NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer, (D) detail of NiCo₂O₄ particles, (E) fresh NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, (F) used NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode.

Figure 3 shows the results of EDS mapping of the Ni mesh modified with NiCo₂O₄ catalyst (NiCo₂O₄/Ni) surface. The distribution of the Ni, Co and O is shown **Figure 3 B–D** respectively. SEM-EDS images show predominantly homogeneous distribution of the catalytic layer, with exception of the small areas close to sharp edges, where the catalytic layer is being visibly peeled-off, most probably due to worse adhesion to the substrate. Interestingly, oxygen distribution map

1
2
3
4 (Figure 3) shows higher level of uniformity, which can be explained by the oxides present on the
5 surface of the Ni mesh substrate.
6
7

39 **Figure 3:** Distribution of selected elements on surface of Ni mesh/NiCo₂O₄ electrode determined by SEM-EDS
40 mapping of surface. (A) SEM image of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode; (B) distribution of Ni; (C) distribution of Co; (D)
41 distribution of O.
42

43 The same analysis was done for the electrodes based on the Ni foam, as shown in **Figure 4** and
44 **Figure 5**. It is seen from the SEM analysis that the morphology of the catalytic layer is not affected
45 by the substrate used. The catalytic layer distribution is homogeneous, which is also confirmed by
46 EDS results shown in **Figure 5**. Comparison of the SEM pictures of the freshly prepared electrode
47 and electrode after testing shows small changes in the morphology as the layer is looser after tests.
48 This is most probably caused by the oxygen evolution and flowing liquid electrolyte, which both
49 have an effect on the morphology of the catalytic layer.
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

Figure 4: Images from scanning electron microscope for: (A) pristine nickel foam, (B) NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode, (C) detail of NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer, (D) detail of NiCo₂O₄ particles, (E) fresh NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode, (F) used NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode.

Figure 5: Distribution of selected elements on surface nickel foam electrode determined by SEM-EDS mapping of surface. (A) SEM image of NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode; (B) distribution of Ni; (C) distribution of Co; (D) distribution of O.

3.2 Electrochemical testing of the OER electrodes

This part of the results presents the complex electrochemical characterization of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrodes and their comparison with pristine nickel-based substrates, which was performed in three different set-ups.

3.2.1 Electrochemical characterization in non-flow arrangement

The polarization curves measured for all tested electrodes under static electrolyte conditions are shown in **Figure 6a**. These curves are internal resistance (IR) corrected based on the ohmic resistance evaluated from EIS measurement at potential of working electrode 0 V vs. RHE. From **Figure 6b** it is clear that using pristine Ni mesh or Ni foam electrodes resulted in different shapes of the polarization curves. Ni foam substrate shows higher values of the overpotential at low current densities, however, from current densities above 15 mA cm⁻² the overpotential increase with higher current density is lower compared to the Ni mesh. At the same time, the potential slope of both the catalytically activated electrodes is much lower than for the pristine Ni electrodes.

Comparing the overpotential needed to reach current density of 10 mA cm^{-2} (η_{10}) the lowest value was achieved by $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ foam electrode (0.334 V) followed by $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ mesh with 0.346 V. On the other hand, the η_{10} values were 0.397 V and 0.44 V for pristine Ni mesh and Ni foam respectively. This is obviously due to the effect of the catalytic layer deposited on the surface of the Ni substrate. Despite the substantial difference in surface area of the Ni substrates (much larger in case of the foam), negligible difference in η_{10} value was observed between $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ mesh and $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ foam. Most probably it was due to the fact that the catalyst loading was the same for both Ni substrates ($1 \text{ mg NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2}$). As the OER is assumed to proceed preferably on the catalyst active sites, the reaction rates for both catalysed electrodes should be comparable. Another explanation can lie in the changed porosity of the Ni substrates. Due to the deposition of the catalytic layer within the Ni foam, the pores are getting smaller, which can reduce the available surface of the 3D electrode. This effect can be further enhanced by the oxygen bubbles evolution and their trapping within the foam.

The potential slope of both pristine electrodes in the region (see **Figure 6a**) is higher when compared to the catalytically activated electrodes. This observation can be explained by different wettability, affecting the adhesion of oxygen bubbles to the surface. It was observed by contact angle measurement that presence of the NiCo_2O_4 catalytic layer increases the wettability of the electrode surface. Ni sheet with deposited NiCo_2O_4 layer showed strong hydrophilic nature, when the contact angle was below four degrees, which was actually below the measurability limit of the device used. Both catalyzed electrodes provided much lower overpotential.

Figure 6: a) Load curves and b) Tafel curves for pristine and catalytically activated Ni substrates at current density $0 - 100 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ and geometric area of electrodes was 1 cm^2 . The potential is IR compensated. Pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). **Working conditions:** $0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ KOH}$, $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, RHE reference electrode, current scan rate of $1 \text{ mA s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

In order to gain deeper information of the properties of the tested electrodes, Tafel analysis of the measured polarisation curves was done (see **Figure 6b** and **Table 3**). Interestingly, in the case of the pristine Ni electrodes, up to three different Tafel slopes were observed. Because the Tafel slope is related to the rate determination step of the electrochemical reaction, its value can be current density dependent as higher reaction rate can be connected with the change of the rate-

determination step. It is also nicely seen from **Figure 6b** that NiCo₂O₄/Ni mesh electrode shows only one Tafel slope in the entire linear part of the Tafel curves, while NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam electrode shows two Tafel slopes.

Table 3: Overview of the electrochemical parameters of the oxygen evaluation reaction obtained from polarisation curves and Tafel analysis.

Mark	Electrode	Tafel slope (mV dec ⁻¹)	j_0 ($\mu\text{A cm}^{-2}$)	η_{10} (V)	R2 (-)
1\$	Ni mesh	70	0.02		0.989
2\$	Ni mesh	186	89	0.3972	0.984
3\$	Ni mesh	447	3,320		0.987
1!	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni mesh	67	0.07	0.3462	0.997
1*	Ni foam	87	0.1		0.988
2*	Ni foam	193	59	0.4399	0.998
3*	Ni foam	353	1,298		0.995
1&	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni foam	84	1.1		0.996
2&	NiCo ₂ O ₄ /Ni foam	145	94	0.3342	0.996

From **Figure 6b** and **Table 3** it is evident, that Tafel slopes increase with the current density. This is especially true for pristine Ni electrodes, which show three different linear parts of the Tafel curve. Values of the Tafel slopes higher than 120 mV dec⁻¹ can be, in some cases, explained by the effect of the active surface coverage by the adsorbents or intermediates, blocking thus the active surface. At the same time, Tafel slopes significantly higher than 120 mV dec⁻¹ can indicate issue with Tafel analysis validity. Because of Tafel analysis represents simplification of the Butler-Volmer equation, one of the assumptions is represented by current density controlled exclusively by the kinetic of the reaction. In the case of the Tafel slopes significantly higher than 120 mV dec⁻¹, the overall performance is probably not limited by the kinetic of the reaction, but by some another parameter.

When j_0 values are compared for pristine Ni electrodes and electrodes modified with NiCo₂O₄ layer for Tafel slopes below 120 mV dec⁻¹, the modified electrodes show higher values of the j_0 , i.e. higher kinetic of the OER.

3.2.2 Electrochemical characterization in a flow electrolysis cell

The prepared OER electrodes were subsequently characterize in a flow electrolysis cell under the conditions more relevant to the final ZAFB application, i.e. using highly alkaline electrolyte and flow-through electrolyte distribution (cell and apparatus construction described in **section 2.3**). It is important to note that despite that electrolysis cell was used, it was operated far away from the standard conditions for alkaline water electrolysis, since 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH electrolyte is used in our system. Overall efficiency of this cell was not considered since main focus was the OER process at positive half-cell. Thus, the full-cell parameters are not discussed in this section.

3.2.3 Mid-term characterization of the prepared OER electrodes

Within this section the initial and mid-term performance and stability of all four OER electrodes (2 pristine and 2 catalytically activated) is compared using *ASR* and overpotential η_{theo} at current

1
2
3
4 density of 50 mA cm^{-2} evaluated from a complex electrochemical characterization under well-
5 defined conditions (for approximately 180 hours), as described in **section 2.4**.
6
7

8 In the **Figure 7a**, the development of potential of studied OER electrodes is shown (measured vs.
9 MOE) during the testing in a laboratory flow electrolysis cell. During the first galvanostatic load
10 period, a gradual decrease of working electrode potential was observed for all four OER electrodes,
11 most probably due to *in situ* cleaning and activation of the electrode surface under the oxidative
12 OER conditions. The highest initial overpotential was exhibited by the pristine Ni mesh, followed
13 by the pristine Ni foam. The rising potential slope of both pristine electrodes over the 5 series is,
14 in absolute values, slightly more significant when compared to the catalytically activated
15 electrodes. This could be explained by the observed differences in the electrode wettability due to
16 the presence of the catalytic layer (discussed in more details in the **chapter 3.2.1**), which may
17 affect the oxygen bubble trapping within the electrodes structures.
18
19
20
21
22
23

Figure 7: **a)** Evolution of OER electrode potential within the mid-term stability experiment for the four Ni-based electrodes: pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). **b)** Initial load curves of the four tested OER electrodes taken from the 1st repetition of series 2; **c)** Load curves for PM and CM electrodes. **d)** Comparison of ASR (left bar) and η_{theo} (right bar, lighter color) evaluated from dynamic load curves. I - after initial stabilization (2nd series, 1st repetition), A - last series before electrolyte exchange (5th series 1st repetition), E - after electrolyte exchange (6th series 2nd repetition). **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte 8 mol dm⁻³ KOH, electrolyte flow rate 160 ml min⁻¹, 20 °C, constant load for 6 hours at 50 mA cm⁻², load curve measurements (0–100 mA cm⁻², 1.25 mA cm⁻² s⁻¹), 5 series (each consists of 5 repetitions) and 2 more repetition after electrolyte change.

As is visible from **Figure 7a**, the potential of all four OER electrodes was gradually rising in time, which was probably due to gradual pH decrease of the working electrolyte caused by OER. Change of the electrolyte composition subsequently led to intensive net flux of water through membrane

(for fluxes direction see **Figure 1c**), approx. 80 – 100 ml (up to 20% of initial volume) of electrolyte moved through the membrane towards CE via combination of osmotic and electroosmotic fluxes during all 5 series (approx. 160 hours). The change of the electrolyte composition is represented by the pH change of working electrolyte, shown in **Table 4**, which summarizes selected parameters evaluated from the load curves including: change of the theoretical overpotential $\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-5}}$ (i.e. with respect to theor. OCP of 0.401 V vs. NHE, at current density 50 mA cm^{-2} , second column); change of the actual overpotential η_{act} (i.e. with respect to actual OCP, third column); change of actual OCP of the working electrode (fifth column) between initial value after system stabilization (1st repetition from series 2) and final value (1st repetition from series 5); change of $\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-6}}$ (at current density 50 mA cm^{-2} , fourth column) after initial stabilization and after electrolyte exchange; and change of pH (last column) between the beginning of experiment and the last repetition before electrolyte exchange. For the detailed parameters description, please see **Table 2**.

Growth of η_{theo} between 2nd and 5th series was significant (see second column of **Table 4**). However, we can see that the corresponding change of $\Delta \eta_{\text{act}}$ remained almost constant, as the actual OCP of working electrolyte also increased due to pH decrease. Therefore, the observed increased η_{theo} are mostly affected by gradual change in electrolyte composition (for detailed discussion see supplementary section 1).

To evaluate the OER electrode under the initial conditions, both electrolytes were exchanged after 5th series (i.e. after 25 repetitions) and two more repetitions of the characterization procedure were performed. The fourth column of **Table 4** shows the comparison of overpotential differences ($\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-6}}$), showing only minor overpotentials increase when compared to the initial values. Interestingly, the overpotential of both pristine OER electrodes decreases in time after the exchange, which is in contrast with behaviour of the catalytically activated electrodes. This phenomenon could be explained by the fact that the surface of pristine nickel is more sensitive to the surface oxidation than the catalytic layer and the concentration of active sites available for the reaction on the electrode surface changes in time and the longer time is needed to achieve steady state. These results confirm that the electrode potential increase was mostly affected by the change of pH of the working electrolyte. In the final application of the electrodes, ZAFB, the electrolyte composition change is much less significant, because the changes caused by OER during battery charging are reversibly compensated by the ORR during the discharge of the battery. Moreover, the use of a single electrolyte tank also suppresses the changes caused by electrolyte constituents permeation through the membrane.

Table 4: Comparison of parameters change between at different stages of experiment evaluated from load curve measurements shown in **Figure 7**.

OER electrode	$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-5}}$ / mV at 50 mA cm^{-2}	$\Delta \eta_{\text{act}}$ / mV at 50 mA cm^{-2}	$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo, s.2-6}}$ / mV at 50 mA cm^{-2}	ΔOCP / mV	ΔpH / -
Details of comparison	between series 2 and 5	between series 2 and 5	between series 2 and 6	between series 2 and 5	between series 1 and 5

Pristine mesh	82	24	14	58	-1.08
Catalysed mesh	75	23	21	44	-1.00
Pristine foam	69	36	3	62	-1.10
Catalysed foam	59	10	18	50	-1.06

Load curves of the OER electrodes constructed from the corresponding load curve measurement (after performance stabilization, i.e. 1st repetition from series 2) are compared in **Figure 7a**. In agreement with trend observed for galvanostatic load measurements, pristine Ni mesh exhibited the highest initial overpotential and *ASR*, while pristine Ni foam showed lower overpotential due to the larger available surface area. From the dynamic load curves measurements, performance of both catalytically activated Ni electrodes seems to be almost the same, while from steady state galvanostatic load measurement we observed slightly lower polarization for the catalytically activated Ni foam. This could indicate different oxygen bubble effect under dynamic and constant polarization when compare NiCo₂O₄ catalyst deposited on the Ni mesh and Ni foam, respectively.

Shape of the load curves in the activation region (approx. 0 – 10 mA cm⁻²) indicates that the mechanism of the OER on the Ni electrode is changed due to the presence of catalytic layer – a short plateau appearing at 0 – 10 mA cm⁻² most probably originates from the surface oxidation of the spinel catalytic layer. In general, the application of the catalytic layer significantly decreases overpotential and *ASR* for OER for both substrate materials: η_{theo} at 50 mA cm⁻² of the electrode with deposited catalytic layer decreased in case of Ni foam substrate by 0.05 V (14% of the value for pristine electrode) and for Ni mesh substrate and by 0.09 V (23%). Comparison of OER electrodes performance (after initial stabilization (I), last series before electrolyte exchange (A) and after electrolyte exchange (E)) for mesh-based electrodes is represented by load curves in **Figure 7b** (only nickel mesh electrode shown for better orientation, all parameter changes are summarized in **Table 4**). For both pristine and catalysed electrodes, the shape of load curve got back to the initial one after the electrolyte exchange, which correlates with the results from galvanostatic loads and confirms promising stability of the developed electrodes.

Catalysed nickel mesh and nickel foam electrodes were characterized after the mid-term stability test by SEM, the resulting images are compared with the initial images in **Figure 2** and **Figure 4** (in **E** and **F** for both mentioned figures). After mid-term stability test, most of the catalytic layer remained at the surface of the nickel substrate. In case of Ni mesh, the presence of more cracks on the electrode surface suggests minor degradation of the catalytic layer. Despite this observation, both catalysed electrodes showed very stable performance within the 180 hours of continuous galvanostatic operation at relatively high current density.

3.2.4 Characterization of OER electrodes in ZAFB single-cell

As shown in **Figure 1c**, the final design of our zinc-air flow battery is a 3-electrode set-up, which consists of three separate cell compartments. Within the negative electrode compartment the graphite felt electrode is located, which serves as substrate for zinc deposition during the battery charging. The OER electrode is located in the middle compartment with independent electrolyte distribution, which is hydraulically separated from the negative electrode compartment by anion exchange membrane. The electronic connection to OER electrode is realized via Ni frame. Third

1
2
3
4 compartment accommodates the gas diffusion electrode for the ORR and it is separated from the
5 middle compartment by micro-porous separator. Both membrane and separator are partially
6 permeable for the electrolyte. The oxygen bubbles evolving during the battery charging decrease
7 the effective cross-section area, increasing internal battery resistance. Moreover, they can be
8 trapped within the OER electrode structure, which is difficult to be recovered. The probability of
9 this phenomenon was expected to be higher for nickel foam due to its lower internal porosity and
10 larger surface area. From this point of view, the use of nickel mesh was anticipated to exhibit lower
11 clogging by bubbles and shadowing of ORR electrode.
12
13
14

15 All four OER electrodes were tested in the final design of our ZAFB single-cell, to observe
16 electrodes performance in the real application incl. the shadowing effect of different electrode
17 matrixes (mesh vs. foam). At first, it is important to mention that during the OER electrodes
18 development, we have modified our ZAFB single-cell construction from the planar substrate to
19 3D carbon felt substrate negative electrode, which significantly increased performance and
20 durability of the battery, when compared to planar substrate. Thus, the previous targeted current
21 density (50 mA cm^{-2}), that was also used for long term galvanostatic loading of the tested
22 electrodes in a flow electrolysis arrangement, was increased to 100 mA cm^{-2} in the final design of
23 ZAFB single-cell.
24
25
26
27

28 The comparison of EIS spectra and load curves measured in 50% SOC (according to zincate
29 concentration in the electrolyte) at the beginning of battery testing is shown in **Figure 8c**, the
30 evaluated parameters are summarized in **Table 5**. The cell ohmic resistance evaluated from the
31 high frequency region of the EIS spectrum was around $1.2\text{--}1.3 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for charging and 1.5--
32 $1.65 \Omega \text{ cm}^2$ for discharging for all 4 cells. Generally higher ASRs for discharge connection is as
33 expected since the ORR electrode is placed behind OER electrode, see **Figure 1c**, thus the inter-
34 electrode distance is larger for discharging cell connection. Ohmic ASR difference between
35 catalysed and pristine electrode from EIS measurements is rather insignificant.
36
37
38
39
40

Figure 8: **a)** EIS spectra (C – charge connection, D – discharge connection), **b)** charging and discharging dynamic load curves and **c)** discharging load curves and power curves of Zn-air battery single-cell for the four tested Ni-based OER electrodes at 50% SOC (with respect to the electrolyte composition); LC-load curve, PC-power curve; **d)** Development of efficiencies (EE – energy efficiency, CE – coulombic efficiency) and capacity utilization (CU – capacity utilization) of during galvanostatic-potentiostatic cycling at 100 mA cm^{-2} ; General conditions: $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 80 ml min^{-1} electrolytes flow rate (0.7 mol dm^{-3} ZnO dissolved in 8 mol dm^{-3} KOH), 200 ml min^{-1} air flow (technical, preheated to $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). PM – pristine mesh, CM – catalyzed mesh, PF – pristine foam, CF – catalyzed foam.

Comparison of the load curves (**Figure 8a**) shows significant differences of the cell polarization during battery charging: the cells with the catalyzed Ni electrode showed significantly lower overvoltage (by about 200 mV at 100 mA cm^{-2}) due to the reduced activation polarization of the electrode. Interestingly, the decrease of the linear part slope of the load curve for catalysed electrodes compared to the pristine electrodes is observed for both charge and discharge part of ZAFB (see ASR_{tot} in **Table 5**). In the other words, the use of catalysed electrodes for OER had also positive effect on the discharging process (see **Figure 8a,b**). Since the ASR_{Ω} values for catalysed electrodes are not significantly lower, the decrease of the $ASR_{\text{tot-d}}$ is probably caused by the different surface properties of the catalytic layers which may accelerate the removal of oxygen bubbles from OER electrode generated during the preceding charging load curve (complete bubble removal takes tens of minutes, see effect of pause between the galvanostatic loads in **Figure 7a**). Hypothesis of the catalytic layer affecting bubble removal is also supported by a slow bending of the discharge load curves in the region of high current densities for cell with the pristine foam electrode, which implies limitation of mass transfer (in terms of products removal).

Table 5: Zn-air battery single-cell parameters for the four tested nickel-based OER electrodes; $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 80 ml min^{-1} electrolytes flow rate (0.7M ZnO dissolved in 8M KOH), 200 ml min^{-1} air flow rate (technical, preheating to $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). ASR evaluated from the EIS and load curve measurements at 50% SOC (in terms of neg. electrolyte), presented at Figure 9. Efficiencies and capacity utilization averaged from the values for 1-20 cycle, presented in **Figure 8**.

	$ASR_{\Omega\text{-c}}$	$ASR_{\Omega\text{-d}}$	$ASR_{\text{tot-c}}$	$ASR_{\text{tot-d}}$	CE	VE	EE	CU
OER electrode	Ohm cm^2	Ohm cm^2	Ohm cm^2	Ohm cm^2	%	%	%	%
Pristine mesh	1.26	1.64	3.00	3.34	95.4	34.8	33.2	77
Catalyzed mesh	1.28	1.64	2.50	3.02	95.4	37.5	35.8	77
Pristine foam	1.30	1.50	2.42	3.56	92.3	34.8	32.1	74

Catalyzed foam	1.20	1.56	2.16	2.84	94.9	44.4	42.1	78
-----------------------	------	------	------	------	------	------	------	----

Figure 8d shows the trends in cell efficiency and capacity utilization for combined galvanostatic-potentiostatic cycling at 100 mA cm^{-2} within 0–80% SOC range (galvanostatic charging, discharge with voltage hold at 0.5 V). The averaged evaluated parameters over 20 cycles are summarised in **Table 5**. From the results it is clear that the pristine nickel OER electrodes exhibit mutually comparable cell parameters (EE of 32–33%), and the application of the Co-Ni spinel catalytic layer increased the voltaic efficiency by about 3% for Ni mesh substrate and even by 10% for the Ni foam substrate. Coulombic efficiencies for all four cells were around 95%, with slightly lower values for the pristine Ni foam, which was most probably related to the poorer performance of the positive ORR (discharging) electrode. No decrease in the capacity utilization or cell short circuit was observed during std. short-term experiments (approx. 3 days) nor for longer testing. The initial energy efficiency of charge-discharge cycle was over 40% for both catalyzed OER electrodes, which is rather high for a battery using an oxygen-based positive half-cell. The observed gradual decrease in voltage and therefore energy efficiency was caused by the increasing polarization of the cell during discharge, probably due to the gradual flooding of the positive ORR (discharge) electrode by electrolyte permeating through the separator from the OER compartment. The hydrophobicity optimization of the catalytic layer of GDE by optimized content of PTFE binder is currently proceeding within our research team and its results are expected to be included within our next publication.

As mentioned in the beginning of this section, it was expected that the nickel foam will cause large shadowing effect to the ORR electrode (when compared to Ni mesh substrate) resulting in higher ohmic *ASR* of the discharging cell. Nevertheless, if we compare ohmic and total resistance for the discharge part of cell for catalysed electrodes, we can see that both values are in fact lower for the nickel foam. Within this study always new ORR electrode with identical composition was used and the cell internal construction thus differs only in OER electrode. Possible explanation of lower $ASR_{\text{tot-d}}$ is that the foam with lower permeability for electrolyte served as better protection against flooding of the ORR electrode when compared to mesh with more open structure. This theory is also supported by the evolution of energy efficiency during the cycling (see **Figure 8d**). Energy efficiency of the cells with Ni foam electrodes are relatively stable over 20 cycles, on the other hand, relatively fast decay of energy efficiency (almost 10 %) is clearly visible in case of Ni mesh electrodes. From these observations we can conclude that although the foam-based electrodes have higher shadowing effect on the ohmic *ASR* in discharge connection, their more compact structure has overall positive effect on the discharge performance of the single-cell. Moreover, it is crucial to pay attention to the homogeneous distribution of the electrolyte flow within the ZAFB to secure effective removal of the evolving oxygen bubbles and prevent the generation of gas bubbles pockets trapped within the OER compartment, which decrease the homogeneity of electrolyte distribution.

3.2.5 Comparison of the achieved results with literature

The measured OCV of the battery in 50% SOC for discharging was approx. 1.5 V and the cell with catalysed Ni foam OER electrode achieved relatively high maximum power density of 150 mW cm⁻² at 40 °C. The value is lower when compared to the highest reported peak power density of 270 mW cm⁻² for zinc-oxygen flow battery [6], but the mentioned study uses pure oxygen (we used air) and, moreover, their oxygen electrodes active area was 2.5 times larger than the zinc electrode one due to the asymmetric cell arrangement used (current and power densities were calculated with respect to the geometric zinc electrode area). This conditions significantly influences the polarization of positive electrodes that has major effect on the battery performance. However, the reported voltage efficiency at room temperature at 100 mA cm⁻² is around 50%, which is comparable to our study (44.4% at 40 °C), taking into account the mentioned differences. Kherzi et al. [27] for their tubular ZAFB single-cell reported the power peak density of 75 mW cm⁻² and the voltage gap (difference between charging and discharging voltage plateau) of 0.84 V at 60 mA cm⁻² (our study 0.93 V at 50 mA cm⁻²), although also here the larger positive electrode area was used due to the tubular cell arrangement. Pichler et al. [25] reported the use of the NiCo₂O₄ (10 mg cm⁻² loading) as a part of the mixture together with La_{0.6}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O₃ (25 mg cm⁻²) as catalytic layer for bi-functional positive electrode in ZAFB. The recorded charging voltage at 50 mA cm⁻² was approx. 1.95 V, i.e. slightly lower compared to our study (2.08 V at same current density), but with 10 times higher catalyst loading. The overall performance of their battery is comparable to our system, reported voltage efficiency was 51% at 50 mA cm⁻² (ours is 44% at 100 mA cm⁻²). To conclude this section, the use of larger air electrodes or increased catalyst loading can improve the performance of ZAFB cell, but the price of air electrode materials must be also considered.

Nonetheless, we demonstrate that our ZAFB single-cell of plane-parallel cell construction with Ni-Co catalytically activated OER electrode can be stably operated at high current density of 100 mA cm⁻² (reasonable target for ZAFB based on [3]), moreover, in a broad SoC range of 0–80%, with relatively high energy efficiency (42.1%) and power density (150 mW cm⁻²) and no capacity fade within the tested period. We believe that the achieved intensification of the ZAFB operation at low catalyst loading and high capacity utilization of the electrolyte is an important step towards the industrial application of the system for stationary energy storage within the ongoing energy transformation.

4. Conclusion

In this contribution we studied oxygen evolution reaction electrodes in alkaline zinc-air flow battery. At first, NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrodes were successfully prepared and characterized by a complex array of physico-chemical methods. Prepared electrodes were subsequently electrochemically tested in three different set-ups. Two set-ups were based on water electrolysis (under flow and non-flow conditions) to suppress zinc electrode instability. The final set-up was the developed three-electrode, three-compartment zinc-air flow battery single-cell with carbon felt negative electrode for zinc deposition and discharging positive gas diffusion electrode for oxygen reduction. In a flow water electrolysis set-up, both catalysed OER electrodes) show significant

1
2
3
4 improvement of performance in terms of lowering overvoltage and area specific resistance. The
5 performance of both catalytically activated electrodes was also confirmed stable during after
6 midterm stability experiments (180 hours for each electrode). Moreover, water management and
7 pH control of the electrolytes was found to have significant influence on the OER electrodes
8 performance.
9

10
11 The characterization in the final set-up of zinc-air flow battery single-cell confirms improved
12 performance of both catalyzed OER electrodes. Use of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrodes efficiently decrease
13 charging overvoltage by 200 mV and therefore increases the voltaic and energy efficiency up to
14 10 %, compared to the pristine electrodes. Interestingly, the nickel foam-based electrodes provided
15 better performance and short-term stability, although they exhibited higher negative shadowing
16 effect to ORR electrode, but in the same time they reduced the flooding of the ORR electrode by
17 the electrolyte and thus extends the life-time of battery. Mean energy efficiency of 42.1% were
18 achieved over 20 combine galvanostatic-potentiostatic cycles at 100 mA cm⁻² for 0–80% SoC
19 range with no capacity utilisation decay for alkaline zinc-air flow battery with NiCo₂O₄/Ni foam
20 OER electrode. At 40 °C and 50% SOC, this cell exhibited low ASR of 2.16 and 2.84 for charging
21 and discharging, respectively and relatively high discharging peak power density of 150 mW cm⁻².
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35

36 Acknowledgments

37
38 This work was supported by the project "The Energy Conversion and Storage", funded as project
39 No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent
40 Research.
41

42 This work was supported by TAČR, program THÉTA2, project no. TK02030001.

43 This work was supported from the grant of Specific university research – grant A1_FCHI_2024_04
44 and A2_FCHI_2024_011.
45

46 We would also like to thank Dr. Jan Dundálek for his pioneering R&D activities on zinc-air
47 storages within our group at Department of Chemical Engineering, which laid the solid foundation
48 for our current studies.
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65

1. Wang, L., et al., *Science mapping the knowledge domain of electrochemical energy storage technology: A bibliometric review*. Journal of Energy Storage, 2024. **77**: p. 109819.
2. Minke, C., U. Kunz, and T. Turek, *Techno-economic assessment of novel vanadium redox flow batteries with large-area cells*. Journal of Power Sources, 2017. **361**: p. 105-114.
3. Li, X., et al., *Chapter 8 - Zinc-based flow batteries for medium- and large-scale energy storage*, in *Advances in Batteries for Medium and Large-Scale Energy Storage*, C. Menictas, M. Skyllas-Kazacos, and T.M. Lim, Editors. 2015, Woodhead Publishing. p. 293-315.
4. Yuan, Z. and X. Li, *Perspective of alkaline zinc-based flow batteries*. Science China Chemistry, 2022.
5. Wu, M., et al., *Self-Reconstruction of Co/Co₂P Heterojunctions Confined in N-Doped Carbon Nanotubes for Zinc–Air Flow Batteries*. ACS Energy Letters, 2021. **6**(4): p. 1153-1161.
6. Bockelmann, M., U. Kunz, and T. Turek, *Electrically rechargeable zinc-oxygen flow battery with high power density*. Electrochemistry Communications, 2016. **69**: p. 24-27.
7. Wang, K., et al., *Advanced rechargeable zinc-air battery with parameter optimization*. Applied Energy, 2018. **225**: p. 848-856.
8. Genthe, S., et al., *Long-Term Performance of a Zinc–Silver/Air Hybrid Flow Battery with a Bifunctional Gas-Diffusion Electrode at High Current Density*. Energy Technology, 2023. **11**(9): p. 2300552.
9. Amunátegui, B., et al., *Electrochemical energy storage for renewable energy integration: zinc-air flow batteries*. Journal of Applied Electrochemistry, 2018. **48**(6): p. 627-637.
10. Hu, C., L. Zhang, and J. Gong, *Recent progress made in the mechanism comprehension and design of electrocatalysts for alkaline water splitting*. Energy & Environmental Science, 2019. **12**(9): p. 2620-2645.
11. Menictas, C., M. Skyllas-Kazacos, and T.M. Lim, *Advances in Batteries for Medium and Large-Scale Energy Storage: Types and Applications*. 2014: Elsevier Science.
12. Lao-atiman, W., et al., *Prediction of charge-discharge behavior and state of charge estimation for tri-electrode rechargeable zinc-air flow batteries*. Journal of Energy Storage, 2022. **55**: p. 105786.
13. Wei, L., et al., *Amorphous Bimetallic Oxide–Graphene Hybrids as Bifunctional Oxygen Electrocatalysts for Rechargeable Zn–Air Batteries*. Advanced Materials, 2017. **29**(38): p. 1701410.
14. Jörissen, L., *Bifunctional oxygen/air electrodes*. Journal of Power Sources, 2006. **155**(1): p. 23-32.
15. Suen, N.-T., et al., *Electrocatalysis for the oxygen evolution reaction: recent development and future perspectives*. Chemical Society Reviews, 2017. **46**(2): p. 337-365.
16. Plevová, M., J. Hnát, and K. Bouzek, *Electrocatalysts for the oxygen evolution reaction in alkaline and neutral media. A comparative review*. Journal of Power Sources, 2021. **507**: p. 230072.
17. Exner, K.S., *Overpotential-Dependent Volcano Plots to Assess Activity Trends in the Competing Chlorine and Oxygen Evolution Reactions*. ChemElectroChem, 2020. **7**(6): p. 1448-1455.

- 1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28
29
30
31
32
33
34
35
36
37
38
39
40
41
42
43
44
45
46
47
48
49
50
51
52
53
54
55
56
57
58
59
60
61
62
63
64
65
18. Yan, Y., et al., *A review on noble-metal-free bifunctional heterogeneous catalysts for overall electrochemical water splitting*. Journal of Materials Chemistry A, 2016. **4**(45): p. 17587-17603.
 19. Yin, J., et al., *NiCo₂O₄-Based Nanosheets with Uniform 4 nm Mesopores for Excellent Zn–Air Battery Performance*. Advanced Materials, 2020. **32**(39): p. 2001651.
 20. Lei, H., et al., *Strongly Coupled NiCo₂O₄ Nanocrystal/MXene Hybrid through In Situ Ni/Co–F Bonds for Efficient Wearable Zn–Air Batteries*. ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces, 2020. **12**(40): p. 44639-44647.
 21. Prabu, M., K. Ketpang, and S. Shanmugam, *Hierarchical nanostructured NiCo₂O₄ as an efficient bifunctional non-precious metal catalyst for rechargeable zinc–air batteries*. Nanoscale, 2014. **6**(6): p. 3173-3181.
 22. Huang, Z., et al., *CoxNi_{1-x}O–NiCo₂O₄/rGO synergistic bifunctional electrocatalysts for high-rate rechargeable zinc–air batteries*. Sustainable Energy & Fuels, 2022. **6**(17): p. 3931-3943.
 23. Maurya, P.K., S. Mishra, and A.K. Mishra, *MoSe₂ and NiCo₂O₄/NiO Based Hybrid Nanostructure as Novel Electrocatalyst for High Performance Rechargeable Zinc-Air Battery*. Electrochimica Acta, 2023. **439**: p. 141689.
 24. Liu, W., et al., *NiCo₂O₄ ultrathin nanosheets with oxygen vacancies as bifunctional electrocatalysts for Zn-air battery*. Applied Surface Science, 2019. **478**: p. 552-559.
 25. Pichler, B., et al., *The impact of operating conditions on component and electrode development for zinc-air flow batteries*. Journal of Applied Electrochemistry, 2018. **48**(9): p. 1043-1056.
 26. Mazúr, P., et al., *Performance evaluation of thermally treated graphite felt electrodes for vanadium redox flow battery and their four-point single cell characterization*. Journal of Power Sources, 2018. **380**: p. 105-114.
 27. Khezri, R., et al., *High current density charging of zinc-air flow batteries: Investigating the impact of flow rate and current density on zinc electrodeposition*. Applied Energy, 2023. **348**: p. 121564.

PM - pristine mesh; CM - catalysed mesh C - Charge
 PF - pristine foam; CF - catalysed foam